

Analysing the Impact of Asset Quality on the Operational Performance of Housing Finance Companies in India

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Abstract

Purpose: Rapid increasing in urbanization leads to demand for Housing Finance Companies is rising significantly. This encourages researcher to go ahead for study towards Housing Sector with different aspects and dimensions. Although, most studies already covered in Housing Finance Sector, and existing studies generally covered the topics such as Comparative Analysis of Housing Finance Companies, measuring financial and Operational performance, and case-based studies. The purpose of this research paper is to analyse the impact of Asset Quality on Operational Performance of Housing Finance Companies in India.

Design/Methodology/Approach: For this study 3 HFC's will be selected based on their Market Capitalization. By using software like Excel and SPSS, the determinants' effect will be analyse with statistical techniques like ANOVA and regression. The Secondary data will be sourced from Reserve Bank of India (RBI), annual reports, regulators, and the NHB.

Findings: It seems likely with the results of this study will throw light on how asset quality influences Housing Finance Companies' (HFCs) operational performance. Indicators which include capital adequacy, gross non-performing assets (GNPAs), and non-performing assets (NPAs) have been utilized to assess asset quality.

Originality/Value: Outcomes of this study becomes relevant for Customers, Regulators, Investors, and Policy maker of HFC's in India. This study will contribute new perspectives and dimensions for further studies.

Keywords

Housing Finance Companies, Operational Performance, Asset Quality.

Introduction

Housing Finance Companies (HFC's) are emerged as significant player among companies in India. HFC's bridges the gap between rise in demand of housing and availability of credit. Rapid growth in urbanization, higher incomes, and many government initiatives encouraging affordable housing represent a number of the factors influencing the increase in housing demand. These drivers have all contributed to rising demand for housing facilities. UN-Habitat anticipates that by 2030, almost 3 billion people, or 40% of the world's population, are going to require access to affordable housing, implying that there will be an ongoing need for about 96,000 housing units globally. (United Nations Human Settlements Programme, n.d.).

Considering the continuing increase in housing demand, monitoring the performance of housing finance companies is a necessity (Julius et al., 2024). In broad terms, Operational and Financial Parameters can be used to determine performance. However, the present study initially aims at examining how financial factors, specially asset quality, affect the operational performance of Indian Housing Finance Companies.

While examining a financial condition of financial institutions, Asset Quality is determine as an essential factor in general (said, 2018). Klein (2013) states that an increase in non-performing loans will make less profitable to financial institutions—specifically, housing finance companies which would cause instability and weaken public confidence. For the purpose to determine asset quality, various countries have created and put into effect legislation that emphasize safety and financial soundness norms, with the goal to prevent any potential issues, these procedures seek to recognize and address asset quality threats early on, and such preventive measures contribute in avoidance of what is regularly referred to as a credit crunch (Bernanke, Lown, and Friedman, 1991). A reduction in asset quality that adversely impacts a bank's financial and operational performance as well as the reliability of the financial system as a whole (Wanjagi, Nasieku, & Fatoki, 2024). In the

present research, net non-performing assets (NNPA) and gross non-performing assets (GNPA) have been utilized as essential indicators of asset quality.

Hence, the primary objective of this research is to analyze the effects of asset quality indicators on the operational performance of housing finance companies. The cost-to-income ratio and total income are two significant factors that are used to evaluate the operational performance and provide insight towards the effectiveness and financial efficiency of the companies.

Objective of study

To examine the impact of Asset Quality on Operational Performance of Housing Finance Companies.

Review of Literature

(Said, 2018) here, the researcher focuses at the association among Return on Equity (ROE), total non-current loans, and leases along with the effects of asset quality on bank profitability. The outcome of this research paper describe the increase of regulations and control of the interest rate.

(Buchory, 2015) this study analyse the effect of credit risk & operations efficiency over the banking profitability. Here, researcher used descriptive method, source of data collection is secondary, and F- test, T- test is used for Hypothesis testing, with the 5% significance level. Study concluded that NPL has significant & positive impact on ROA, and Cost to income ratio has negative and significant impact on ROA.

(Enock & Joshua, 2024) here researcher tries to determine the effect of capital structure on the financial parameters of real estate companies in Uganda. The aim this research is to analyse the correlation among components of Capital Structure including Debt-to-equity ratio, long term debt, and total asset and indicators of financial parameters such as Return on Assets and Return on Equity.

(Chadha & Chawla, 2013) here, researcher examine the Financial Parameters of the Housing Finance Companies in India with last five year data by using CAMEL Model. To select the HFC's Purposive Sampling is used, & F- test is used for Hypothesis testing. The study concluded that GRUH is at first ranked, HDFC & GIC secured the second and third ranked under CAMEL Model.

(Kweh, Lu, & Ming Liu, 2024) in this study researcher tries to examines how profitability in banks get influenced by efficient resource management by using DEA model through dynamic network structure. Researcher analyse 287 U.S. commercial banks for the period 2010-2020, with CAMEL Model. C for capital adequacy, A for asset quality, M for management quality, E for earning ability & L for liquidity. Findings of this study is that banks have a 55.4%, for performance improvement, with efficient banks whose CAMEL rating are stronger.

It has been found from these previous research studies that there is an absence of literature regarding the way financial parameters affect the operational performance of housing finance companies. This study examines how asset quality impact operational performance.

The present research intends to address this gap by examining how important financial parameters, especially asset quality influence the operational performance of housing finance companies in India. By evaluating these factors, the study aims to bring more light on the numerous manners in which asset quality impacts HFCs' overall operational efficacy, income generation, and cost effectiveness.

Methodology

Research Desgin - This study is empirical and analytical in nature. The primary purpose why it is analytical in nature is because it evaluates financial and operational data in order to seek for patterns and relationships between significant elements. The approach is empirical and therefore uses real data and reliable evidences to assess hypotheses and validate results. This dual approach assures both theoretical depth and practical relevance.

Source of Data: Data collected from the Annual reports of Housing finance companies, Reserve Bank of India, websites of HFC's, National Housing Bank, Regulatory authorities.

Sampling

For selection of Housing Finance Companies Purposive Sampling is used for study. Hence, 3 HFC's are selected for the study that are- LIC Housing Finance, PNB Housing Finance, and Can fin Housing Finance.

Tools Used

In this study Regression method is used to examine the influence of Asset Quality on the Operational Performance with the help of Statistical Software SPSS.

Statistics Used in the Study

Asset Quality is Independent Variable and Operational Performance is Dependent Variable.

Asset Quality is measured by Gross Non-Performing Assets and Net Non-Performing Assets; and Operational Performance is measured by cost to income ratio, and Total Income Growth.

Analysis

LIC Housing Finance

Dependent Variable: Cost-to-Income Ratio

Predictor	β	t	Sig. (p)
GNPA	1.916	3.037	0.093
NNPA	-1.234	-1.956	0.190
Model	—	—	R ² = 0.870; F = 6.672 (0.130)

Dependent Variable: Total Income Growth

Predictor	β	t	Sig. (p)
GNPA	0.785	1.127	0.377
NNPA	-1.578	-2.265	0.152
Model	—	—	R ² = 0.841; F = 5.290 (0.159)

To evaluate the effect of Asset Quality by using variable GNPA, NNPA on the Operational Performance of LIC Housing Finance Company is conducted by using Regression model. To measure Operational Performance of HFC's Cost to income ratio, and Total income growth is taken as dependent variable. When the Cost to income ratio is taken for analysis the model represents a highest explanatory power i.e. R² = 0.870, whereas, the regression model represent insignificant result i.e. F=6.672, p= 0.130. However, at the 5% level, GNPA (p=0.093) and NNPA (p=0.190) each have a negligible effect on the cost-to-income ratio. Additionally, an analysis of the next dependent variable, total income increase, reveals a good explanatory power (R² = 0.841), whereas the model as a whole revealed a statistically insignificant impact (F = 5.290, p = 0.159). Both GNPA (p=0.377) as well as NNPA (p=0.152) were shown to have no noticeable effect on the growth of total income. Thus, the Null Hypothesis has been accepted, conforming by the overall conclusion of the regression result for LIC Housing Finance Company. Within the study period, LIC Housing Finance Company has not been significantly influenced by asset quality.

PNB Housing Finance

Predictor	β	t	Sig. (p)
GNPA	-1.323	-0.253	0.824
NNPA	1.173	0.224	0.844
Model	—	—	R ² = 0.050; F = 0.052 (0.950)

Dependent Variable: Cost-to-Income Ratio

Predictor	β	t	Sig. (p)
GNPA	3.101	1.164	0.364
NNPA	-2.308	-0.867	0.477
Model	—	—	R ² = 0.754; F = 3.063 (0.246)

Dependent Variable: Total Income Growth

The Regression analysis is done for PNB Housing Finance Company to analyse the effect of Asset Quality on Operational performance of a Company. GNPA and NNPA have been used as an independent variables for asset quality, whereas the cost to income ratio and total income growth are employed as dependent variables for operational performance.

Regression analysis of the cost-to-income ratio demonstrated a very weak explanatory power ($R^2 = 0.050$) and statistical insignificance ($F = 0.05$, $p = 0.950$), showing that the variable of asset quality didn't explain any significant changes in the cost-to-income ratio. GNPA ($p=0.824$) and NNPA ($p=0.844$) have been determined to have statistically insignificant effects on the cost-to-income ratio. Similarly, the regression model proved statistically insignificant ($F = 3.063$, $p = 0.245$) and explained a significant portion of variation ($R^2 = 0.754$) when the next dependent variable, total income increase, was assessed. The statistical effects of both GNPA ($p=0.364$) and NNPA ($p=0.477$) on total income growth is insignificant. As result, the null hypothesis has been accepted, and PNB Housing Finance Company's asset quality has no significant effect on the company's operational performance.

Can Fin Home Finance

Predictor	β	t	Sig. (p)
GNPA	1.656	2.526	0.127
NNPA	-2.043	-3.116	0.089
Model	—	—	$R^2 = 0.835$; $F = 5.053$ (0.165)

Dependent Variable: Cost-to-Income Ratio

Predictor	β	t	Sig. (p)
GNPA	-0.208	-0.147	0.897
NNPA	-0.276	-0.194	0.864
Model	—	—	$R^2 = 0.223$; $F = 0.287$ (0.777)

Dependent Variable: Total Income Growth

The Regression Analysis of Can Fin Home finance was done to analyse the effect of Asset Quality with the variable GNPA & NNPA on operational performance by using variable cost to income ratio, & Total income growth. When the cost-to-income ratio is evaluated, the regression model possesses very high explanatory power ($R^2 = 0.835$); but the overall model's statistical value ($F = 5.053$) was statistically insignificant ($p = 0.165$). At the 5% level, GNPA ($p=0.127$) and NNPA ($p=0.089$) respectively had a statistically insignificant influence on the dependent variable, corresponding to the cost to income ratio. Considering the second dependent variable, total income growth, study revealed a regression model with a comparatively low explanatory power ($R^2 = 0.233$), that was insignificant in statistical terms ($F = 0.287$, $p = 0.777$). Additionally, the results for GNPA ($p=0.897$) and NNPA ($p=0.864$) showed statistically insignificant effects on the rise of total income. performance within the examination phase. As an outcome, Can Fin Home Finance's overall results accepted the null hypothesis, which suggests that asset quality had no significant impact on operational performance within the study period.

Conclusion

The present research study examined how Asset Quality of a selected Housing Finance Companies impact the Operational Performance. LIC Housing Finance, PNB Housing Finance, and Can Fin Home Finance have been selected throughout this study. Gross non-performing assets (GNPA) and net non-performing assets (NNPA) having an impact on asset quality. Asset quality has little or no effect on operational performance as assessed by the cost-to-income ratio and total income growth, according to the regression results obtained from all three housing finance companies for the years 2020–2024. Regression analysis's combined effect is statistically insignificant, and at the 5% level, GNPA and NNPA's individual effects were simultaneously shown to be insignificant. However, when considering the R^2 value, the regression model also shows a very high explanatory power. As an outcome, concluding the study's results, that the null hypothesis which indicates that asset quality showed no noticeable impact on HFCs' operational performance within the time period of the study.

For future research, researchers may raise the sample size for HFCs, prolong the study period, and examine other indications in subsequent studies.

Limitation of the Study

The analysis for this research is limited to three Housing Finance Companies only, which may be not applicable to overall Housing Sector in India. Additionally, the time period for

this research is restricted to only five Financial Years, which may be not sufficient data to represent long term trends in Financial Performance.

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